

SOME ASPECTS OF CONGENITAL PNEUMONIA IN PREMATURE NEWBORNS

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Abstract. *The aim of the study was to investigate perinatal risk factors and the clinical features of congenital pneumonia in premature newborns. A total of 156 premature infants were included in the study, divided into two groups: Group 1 (primary group) consisting of 80 premature infants with congenital pneumonia, and Group 2 (comparison group) consisting of 76 premature infants with acute respiratory infections. The research employed clinical-anamnestic, clinical-laboratory, instrumental, and statistical methods. Among the significant risk factors for congenital pneumonia in premature infants, the most notable in their mothers were a complicated obstetric history, pregnancy-related pathologies, anemia, and infectious diseases. In premature infants with congenital pneumonia, especially those with perinatal CNS lesions, the most frequent clinical signs were combinations of apnea, wheezing, and sputum production, observed in 82.3±3.7% to 85.0±5.2% of cases.*

Objective of the study. *To examine perinatal risk factors and the clinical course characteristics of congenital pneumonia in premature newborns.*

Materials and methods. *A total of 156 premature newborns were examined, including: Primary group (Group 1): 80 premature infants with congenital pneumonia. Comparison group (Group 2): 76 premature newborns with acute respiratory infection. Clinical-anamnestic, clinical-laboratory, instrumental, and statistical research methods were used.*

Results. *Among the risk factors in mothers of premature newborns with congenital pneumonia, in addition to a complicated obstetric history and pregnancy pathology, anemia and infectious diseases are of the greatest significance.*

Among the clinical signs in premature infants with congenital pneumonia against the background of perinatal CNS lesions, the most common (ranging from 82.3±3.7% to 85.0±5.2%) are combinations of symptoms such as apnea, wheezing, and sputum production.

Keywords: *congenital pneumonia, perinatal risk factors, premature newborn.*

Introduction. Congenital Pneumonia is an acute infectious-inflammatory disease of the respiratory sections of the lungs resulting from ante- and/or intranatal infection, with clinical and radiological manifestations appearing within the first 72 hours of a newborn's life [1].

In the structure of perinatal morbidity and mortality, respiratory disorders including congenital pneumonia, play a significant role [2]. According to some data, congenital pneumonia was the primary cause of stillbirth in 0.35% of cases and accounted for 8.34% of neonatal deaths within the first six days of life [3].

The clinical condition of newborns with congenital pneumonia worsens in the presence of multiple risk factors and severe comorbidities [4-6]. Preterm birth and prematurity remain pressing issues in both obstetrics and neonatology. Currently, the rate of preterm births varies widely across different countries, ranging from 5% to 18% [7-9].

In the early neonatal period, extremely preterm infants are most commonly affected by sepsis and congenital infections. Regardless of the level of infant mortality, the leading causes of neonatal death remain prematurity and congenital pneumonia [10-11].

Morphofunctional immaturity of organs and systems in this group of newborns predisposes them to the development of diseases that are often incompatible with life. Neonatal lung diseases are particularly common in premature newborns [11-13].

A key factor in this process is transamniotic infection of lung fluid, which leads to the formation of hyaline membranes and the development of respiratory failure in the newborn. At the same time, perinatal fetal hypoxia, caused by chronic placental insufficiency, disrupts antenatal lung development [14].

The most frequent manifestations of various pathological processes in the early neonatal period among premature infants are respiratory disorders, which may indicate congenital pneumonia, severe respiratory distress syndrome, or generalized infection. The nonspecific nature of clinical symptoms associated with these pathological conditions presents significant challenges in differential diagnosis, especially in extremely preterm infants.

Objective of the study perinatal risk factors and the clinical course characteristics of congenital pneumonia in premature newborns.

Materials and methods. A total of 156 newborns were examined at the neonatal pathology departments of City Hospital No. 5 and the maternity wards of the Republican Perinatal Center in Tashkent. All newborns were divided into two groups:

Primary group (Group 1): 80 premature newborns with congenital pneumonia.

Comparison group (Group 2): 76 premature newborns in the second stage of postnatal care with acute respiratory infection.

To study perinatal risk factors, we analyzed medical history data obtained from neonatal development records (Form 097/x), medical records (Form 003/x), and direct interviews with mothers of the observed newborns. Clinical examination and dynamic monitoring of newborns were conducted. General clinical and laboratory studies, neurosonography, and radiography were performed.

Statistical processing of the obtained results was carried out using the Fisher-Student method. Differences between the compared values were considered statistically significant at $p < 0.05$.

Results and discussion. Among newborns in Group 1, 35.0% had a gestational age of 30–33 weeks, while 65.0% were born at 34–36 weeks. In Group 2, all premature infants had a gestational age of 35–36 weeks.

All newborns in Group 1 (100%) were diagnosed with congenital pneumonia and hypoxic-ischemic encephalopathy (HIE) of grades 1–2. In Group 2, 94% of premature infants in the second stage of postnatal care exhibited HIE of grades 1–2.

Maternal Socio-Biological Factors. The analysis of maternal socio-biological factors showed no significant differences between the groups. Among all mothers:

6.4% were aged 17–19 years

33.3% were aged 20–30 years

60.3% were 30 years or older

Regarding educational background:

46.2% had higher education

21.8% had secondary specialized education

32.0% had only a secondary education

Analysis of parity revealed:

39.7% were primiparous

47.4% were multiparous

12.9% had multiple previous births

Perinatal Risk Factors. An analysis of obstetric history showed that complicated obstetric history was significantly more common in Group 1 (37.5%) compared to Group 2 (26.3%).

Pregnancy complications included:

Threatened miscarriage: 67.5% in Group 1, versus 34.2% in Group 2

Gestational toxicosis: 42.5% in Group 1, 2.7 times more frequent than in Group 2 (15.8%)

Fetoplacental insufficiency: 12.5% in Group 1, 7.8% in Group 2

Maternal Morbidity

Anemia was diagnosed in 62.5% of Group 1 mothers, which was 8 times higher than in Group 2 (7.8%)

Chronic somatic diseases were present in 12.5% of Group 1 mothers, including:

Congenital heart defects (CHD): 2.5%

Chronic arterial hypertension: 5.0%

Pyelonephritis: 2.5%

Cholecystitis: 2.5%

In Group 2, chronic diseases were more frequent (26.3%), including:

Chronic arterial hypertension: 15.8%

Pyelonephritis: 10.5%

Infectious Pathology. Infectious diseases were 3.4 times more common in Group 1 than in Group 2 ($p < 0.001$).

In Group 1, infections were recorded in 62.5% of cases:

Acute respiratory viral infections (ARVI): 40.0%

TORCH infections: 22.5%

In Group 2, infections were detected in 18.4% of cases (ARVI only).

Neonatal Respiratory Disorders

Respiratory distress syndrome (RDS) occurred in $40.9 \pm 5.2\%$ of newborns in Group 1, 1.9 times more frequently than in Group 2 ($21.1 \pm 4.9\%$).

CPAP (Continuous Positive Airway Pressure) was required in $12.5 \pm 3.5\%$ of newborns in Group 1, significantly more than in Group 2 ($2.6 \pm 2.5\%$, $p < 0.01$).

Mechanical ventilation (MV) was needed twice as often in Group 1 ($12.5 \pm 3.5\%$) compared to Group 2 ($6.7 \pm 3.1\%$).

A comparative analysis of the frequency of clinical symptoms associated with infection was conducted (see table 1).

Among all the studied clinical signs, a significant proportion occurred more frequently in premature newborns with congenital pneumonia. These included:

Dyspnea

Apnea

Cough

Febrile temperature

Weakened breath sounds
 Lung rales
 Sputum production
 Hepatosplenomegaly
 Leukopenia
 Thrombocytopenia

In contrast, premature infants with acute respiratory infections exhibited a higher frequency of:

Catarrhal symptoms
 Subfebrile temperature

Symptoms such as encephalopathy manifestations, pallor, or cyanosis were observed in the vast majority of infants in both groups.

Symptom Combinations in Congenital Pneumonia. Analysis of symptom co-occurrence in premature infants with pneumonia revealed that:

Two symptoms together (e.g., apnea + rales, apnea + sputum, rales + sputum) appeared in 82.5±3.7% of cases.

A combination of three symptoms (apnea, rales, and sputum production) was found in 85.0±5.2% of cases.

Table 1. Frequency of Clinical Manifestations of Congenital Pneumonia in Premature Newborns

Clinical Manifestation	Group 1 (% , n = 80)	Group 2 (% , n = 76)	p-value
Encephalopathy symptoms	100.0	94.7 ± 3.6	p > 0.05
Pallor or cyanosis	92.5 ± 3.9	81.6 ± 5.7	p > 0.05
Catarrhal symptoms	7.5 ± 3.1	94.7 ± 3.7	p < 0.001
Dyspnea	27.5 ± 4.7	5.3 ± 2.9	p < 0.001
Tachypnea	20.0 ± 4.9	21.1 ± 4.7	p > 0.05
Apnea	87.5 ± 3.2	10.5 ± 3.9	p < 0.001
Cough	52.5 ± 5.1	5.3 ± 4.2	p < 0.001
Subfebrile temperature	32.5 ± 5.9	78.9 ± 5.3	p < 0.001
Febrile temperature	67.5 ± 6.2	10.5 ± 4.1	p < 0.001
Weakened breath sounds	72.5 ± 4.3	35.0 ± 3.7	p < 0.001
Auscultatory rales	95.5 ± 3.7	0	p < 0.001
Sputum production	77.5 ± 3.9	0	p < 0.001
Hepatosplenomegaly	17.5 ± 4.1	5.3 ± 2.4	p < 0.01
Hemorrhagic syndrome	15.0 ± 3.5	5.3 ± 2.7	p < 0.01
Neutrophilic leukocytosis	12.5 ± 3.2	15.7 ± 5.9	p > 0.05
Leukopenia	22.5 ± 5.3	0	p < 0.001
Thrombocytopenia	45.2 ± 3.8	5.2 ± 2.7	p < 0.001

Radiological Findings. X-ray abnormalities in newborns with congenital pneumonia were associated with:

Signs of pulmonary immaturity

Presence of respiratory distress syndrome (RDS)

The severity of X-ray findings correlated with the severity of the infant's condition and respiratory impairment.

Conclusion. At present, socio-biological risk factors remain among the most significant contributors to preterm birth. Among mothers of premature newborns with congenital pneumonia, the most important risk factors, in addition to:

Complicated obstetric history

Pregnancy pathology are:

Maternal anemia

Infectious diseases

Congenital pneumonia in preterm infants commonly develops against a background of perinatal CNS damage. The most frequent clinical symptom combinations in these newborns include apnea, rales, and sputum production.

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